

ARIES

Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society

Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 730871

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Evaluation of systems 1 and 2

DELIVERABLE: D15.2

Document identifier:	ARIES-D15.2
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 24 (April 2019)
Report release date:	30/04/2019
Work package:	WP15: Thin Film for Superconducting RF Cavities
Lead beneficiary:	STFC
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

Following the WP15 program two superconducting systems (Nb_3Sn as System 1 and NbN as System 2) were studied in a single layer in terms of deposition parameters (substrate material and surface preparation, temperature, base and deposition partial pressure of reactive (N_2) and non-reactive (Ar and Kr)), film characterisation (structure and composition) and DC superconducting properties. It has been shown that System 1 (Nb_3Sn) can be successfully deposited from an alloy target and demonstrate good SC properties when it is deposited at high temperature (around 550-650 °C).

System 2 (NbN) can be produced from an Nb metal target by reactive sputtering in N_2 rich atmosphere. A few SIS structures have been investigated using Nb as a base layer followed by AlN and Nb_3Sn as insulating and superconducting screening layer. For a practicality of SIS structure deposition, the screening layer materials should be one containing nitrogen such as NbN and NbTiN, especially when insulation layer is AlN.

The finding should be finally applied to QPR samples and tested at RF conditions as a part of WP15 programme in the following years.

ARIES Consortium, 2019

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 730871. ARIES began in May 2017 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

RF cavities made of bulk Nb or coated with a Nb film have reached their performance limits. The aim of the work reported here was to explore alternative superconductor materials such as Nb₃Sn (System 1) and NbN (System 2). This report is summarising the validation of deposition process and subsequently, surface and structural analysis, DC superconductivity evaluation of NbN and Nb₃Sn in a single layer. Deposition parameters for successful depositing of the Nb₃Sn and NbN films with superconducting properties were determined in a series of experiments at STFC and University of Siegen, respectively. The DC superconducting properties of the films were demonstrated by DC magnetometry at IEE and STFC.

Another possibility of enhancing the superconducting RF performance of SRF cavities is employing multilayer coating consisting of alternating superconducting and insulating layers, such as Superconductor-Insulator-Superconductor (SIS). WP15 team have looked at the Nb as a base layer followed by AlN and Nb₃Sn as insulating and superconducting screening layer deposited on copper and sapphire substrate. The finding of single layer deposition were further explored for depositing multilayers. Four SIS samples have been produced demonstrating correct structure and expected critical temperature for each superconducting layer of different materials.

1. Introduction

Bulk niobium (Nb) has been the material of choice for superconducting RF (SRF) cavities since it has the highest critical temperature ($T_c = 9.25$ K) and the highest superheating magnetic field H_{sh} of all the pure metals and it can be formed easily in cavity shape. The RF performance of bulk Nb cavities has continuously improved over the years and is approaching the optimal performance achievable ($H_{sh} \sim 210$ mT) [1]. Although further improvement has been achieved with nitrogen surface doping [2–5], long term solutions for SRF surface efficiency enhancement need yet to be pursued.

The optimal material may depend on the type of facility. For low-duty-cycle high energy linacs, an alternative material would be chosen that can sustain very large surface magnetic fields, as this is what fundamentally limits the accelerating gradient E_{acc} , and therefore sets the minimum number of cavities required to reach a given energy. On the other hand, for modern CW SRF linac designs, cryogenics is the cost driver, not the number of cavities. For niobium, a low surface resistance (R_s) operation requires the cavity to be cooled to 1.9 K, where cryogenic efficiency often pushes the cost-optimum arrangement to using only modest gradients, because losses go quadratically with E_{acc} .

At ~ 2 K, cavities made from an alternative material with lower R_s than niobium would have smaller losses at a given E_{acc} , so they would allow the cryogenic plant to be smaller and require less grid power, or they could operate at higher gradients, and therefore require fewer cavities. Furthermore, the temperature dependent part of R_s scales with $\exp(T_c/T)$, so if the alternative material had a large T_c , low R_s operation could be possible at 4.2 K, greatly simplifying the cryogenic plant by allowing it to operate at atmospheric pressure. Low R_s operation at even higher temperatures would open up the possibility of using helium gas for cooling.

To determine which superconductors are viable candidates for producing high-performing SRF cavities, one should look for certain properties. To achieve large E_{acc} , a large superheating field H_{sh} is desirable. Below H_{c1} , the material is in the complete Meissner state. In the DC condition, flux penetration starts above H_{c1} . The material becomes finely divided in normal and superconductive domains in periodic arrangements, called flux vortices. However, if the nucleation time of a vortex is much larger than the RF period, it is possible for the Meissner state to metastably persist above H_{c1} , up to a field defined as the superheating field H_{sh} [4]. For type-II superconductors, with a Ginzburg-Landau parameter $\kappa = \lambda/\xi \gg 1$, H_{sh} has been calculated to be $\sim 0.75H_c$, where H_c is the thermodynamic critical field:

$$H_c = H_{c2}/\sqrt{2}\kappa.$$

Another important parameters is the surface resistance R_s , which is a sum of two parts:

$$R_s = R_{BCS}(T) + R_{res},$$

where R_{BCS} is the BCS resistance derived from the Bardeen–Cooper–Schrieffer (BCS) theory; and R_{res} is a residual resistance due to parasitic losses. $R_{BCS} \propto e^{-T_c/T}$ while R_{res} is independent of temperature. The residual resistance is not fully understood yet but believed to be due to intrinsic

losses, due to non-ideal surface quality, metallic inclusions within the penetration depth, the presence of oxides on the surface, and grain boundaries. Other contributors are extrinsic losses due to flux trapped during cooling. Due to the wide variety of phenomena, it is impossible to predict these residual losses with one formula. However, from results reported in literature, R_{res} is found empirically to be at least proportional to $\sqrt{\rho_n}$, where ρ_n is the material conductivity at room temperature. Therefore, for a material with the same BCS resistance but different T_c and ρ_n , **the lower ρ_n , the lower R_{res} .**

Also alternative material must also possess the following qualities:

1. It must be possible to fabricate it in a way that it conforms to a complex geometry over large area;
2. It must have decent thermal conductivity (and be able to be deposited on a substrate with decent thermal conductivity) for cooling to avoid thermal runaway;
3. It must have minimal surface roughness to avoid field enhancement;
4. It must be able to be made clean (for example, it cannot release potentially field emitting dust, and there must be a method to clean surface contaminants without affecting quality).

Some of the most promising alternative SRF materials and relevant properties are shown in Table 1, along with those of niobium.

Table 1: Some superconducting parameters for materials considered for SRF applications.

Material	T_c (K)	ρ_n ($\mu\Omega\text{cm}$)	$H_c(0)$ (T)	$H_{c1}(0)$ (T)	$H_{c2}(0)$ (T)	λ (nm)	Δ (meV)	ξ (nm)
Nb	9.23	2	0.2	0.18	0.28	40	1.5	35
NbN	17.3	70	0.23	0.02	15	200-350	2.6	3 - 5
NbTiN	17.8	35	-	0.03	15	150-200	2.8	5
Nb ₃ Sn	18	8-20	0.54	0.05	28	80-100	3.1	4
V ₃ Si	17	4	0.72	0.072	24.5	179	2.5	3.5
Nb ₃ Al	18.7	54	-	-	33	210	3	-
Mo ₃ Re	15	10-30	0.43	0.03	3.5	140	-	-
MgB ₂	40	0.1-10	0.43	0.03	3.5-60	140	2.3-7.2	5
Pnictides	30-55	-	0.5-0.9	30	50-135	200	10 - 20	2

Another approach for increasing E_{acc} in SRF cavities was suggested by Gurevich in 2006 [1] by creating SIS multilayer structures where superconducting layers (S) are separated by an insulator layer (I).

Following the WP15 program two systems (NbN and Nb₃Sn) were studied in a single layer in terms of deposition parameters (substrate material and surface preparation, temperature, base and deposition partial pressure of reactive (N₂) and non-reactive (Ar and Kr)), film characterisation (structure and composition) and DC superconducting properties. The sample substrate preparation is based on cleaning and polishing procedure reported in Delivery Report D15.1 [6].

A few SIS structures have been investigated using Nb as a base layer followed by AlN and Nb₃Sn as insulating and superconducting screening layer, respectively.

The finding should be finally applied to QPR samples and tested at RF conditions as a part of WP15 programme in the following years.

2. System 1 - Niobium-3-Tin (Nb₃Sn) and SIS structures at STFC

2.1. DEPOSITION FACILITY

A purpose-built deposition system was used to deposit superconducting thin films. A schematic view of the deposition system is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Schematic view of the experimental deposition system.

Figure 2: Photographs of the entire deposition facility: (a) deposition chamber, (b) load-lock chamber, (c) entire facility.

The entire deposition facility can be seen in Fig. 2 and comprises two chambers; a load-lock chamber and deposition chamber. The deposition chamber comprises an 18 inch diameter spherical chamber with nine ports and an adjoining six way cross piece which houses vacuum gauges and two turbomolecular pumps (TMP). A UHV Design ECP-9442-004 substrate heater and biasing stage is seated at the base of the spherical chamber. The substrate heater can heat sample substrates up to ≈ 900 °C and is powered by a Glassman Europe Limited LV (60 V, -50 A) DC Power Supply. The biasing stage allows the substrate to be either grounded using a 50 Ohm impedance RF block, or to be DC or RF biased. Only DC biasing was tested during the study using a TDK-Lambda Genesys 1U power supply with the sample being insulated from the chamber walls when biased. The biasing stage rotates the sample at 4 rpm. The deposition chamber contains ports which allow the installation of up to four magnetrons, however only three were used in this study, facing downwards towards the substrate at an angle of 45° . Each magnetron is a 3 inch planar magnetron. One magnetron is mounted on an adjustable bellow allowing movement in the z direction between 50 and 250 mm from the substrate surface, the other magnetron is fixed at 150 mm from the substrate surface. The magnetrons are powered by either an Ionautics Hipster 1000 V HiPIMS power supply or a 3kW Advanced Energy Pinnacle + Pulsed DC / DC dual output power supply. A quartz window is situated on one of the side ports of the deposition chamber and allows an ex-situ viewing lens to face the magnetron plasma. The viewing lens is connected via an optical cable to a Plasus Emicon multi-channel plasma emission monitoring and process control system that is used to identify ionised species within the magnetron plasma during deposition.

The deposition chamber contains an MKS 104220009 Penning gauge, an MKS 103170024SH Pirani gauge and an MKS 120AA-00001RAJ Baratron gauge. The Penning and Pirani gauges output to an MKS 937B Gauge Controller and the Baratron to an MKS PR400B controller. The Penning gauge has a measurement range between 10^{-11} to 10^{-3} mbar, the Pirani gauge can measured between 10^{-3} and 10^3 mbar and the Baratron gauge is accurate between 10^{-4} and 10^{-1} mbar. Up to two different

process gases can be injected into the deposition chamber by separate MKS 1179A12CS1BVB mass flow controllers, one calibrated for krypton and the other for nitrogen. The mass flow controllers have a flow range up to 100 sccm and are controlled by MKS Type 250B and MKS Model 247C control units. Pressure during deposition is typically 10^{-3} mbar and is set by adjusting the flow rate through the mass flow controller, with a constant pumping speed, until the desired pressure is read from the Baratron. A Leybold 340M TMP used to pump the deposition chamber is connected directly to an 8 inch diameter pumping port. A butterfly valve is connected directly to the 8 inch port, which is used for reducing the pumping speed during deposition. The restricted pumping speed is used during deposition to conserve sputter gas.

The loadlock chamber of the deposition facility is built around a six-way cross piece with 8 inch diameter ports. The loadlock chamber houses similar Penning and Pirani gauges as described for the deposition chamber, plus an MKS MicroVision2 residual gas analyser (RGA). The RGA is a type of mass spectrometer that can measure the mass to charge ratio of residual gas ions. The mass to charge ratio can be used to determine the composition of the residual gasses within the vacuum system. The RGA can only work at pressures below 10^{-5} mbar and is therefore unsuitable for use in the deposition chamber. A variable pumping system was installed between load lock and deposition chamber which allows a small volume of process gas to be sent through a leak valve for analysis by the RGA. Up to 7 samples can be loaded into a retractable cartridge system within the load lock chamber. Sample substrates are usually disks <100 mm in diameter to be installed within the cartridge. Smaller substrates can be used with the cartridge but must be placed on top of a 100 mm copper disk. Only one sample can be inserted into the system at a time when not using the cartridge. The sample temperature during deposition was measured using a thermocouple located at the heater filament. Another retractable thermocouple is mounted inside the deposition chamber which can measure the substrate temperature by direct contact. An efficient bakeout procedure, combining heater tapes and the substrate heater, was devised to minimise the lost process time when changing samples or changing the targets of the magnetrons. After each air exposure the chamber is baked to achieve a pressure of 10^{-10} mbar.

2.2. SAMPLE PREPARATION

The main substrates used in this study were 2-mm thick copper (either in square shape 53 mm × 53 mm or 2-inch diameter disk) and 2-inch diameter c-plane sapphire. In most of cases witness samples of (tantalum and sapphire) for different analysis were used as shown in Fig. 3. Ta and sapphire were used because it has the almost the same lattice parameters as Nb and can be elevated to high temperature.

For achieving the maximum temperature possible a cut out was made in the sample holder plate so the main substrate can be heated directly. The difference in temperature between the main substrate and the witness samples was found to be in order of 25 to 30°C.

The effect of substrate surface polishing with different polishing procedure on superconducting thin films was studied by WP15 in 1st year of ARIES and has been reported in Delivery Report D15.1 [6]. It was concluded to prepare copper samples either with EP or SUBU (see glossary at the end of report). Tantalum and sapphire substrates were degreased in ultrasonic bath of acetone, ethanol and isopropanol alcohol (IPA) for 10 minutes and then rinsed with deionised water and dried with dry nitrogen prior to being introduced into load lock chamber.

The deposition targets used in this study were high purity Nb (RRR = 300) and Al. The alloy targets used were Nb₃Sn and Nb₃Ge with atomic percent of 75/25 ratio. The list of all samples prepared in this study is shown in Table 2. After each sample loading in the load lock, the load lock was baked for 24 hours. Prior each deposition the transferred substrate in the deposition chamber was heated to 600 °C for 15 hours. For deposition the substrate temperature was either raised or reduced to deposition temperature. This was done to condition the chamber prior to deposition and also to remove any oxide from the copper surface.

Figure 3: Image of sample plate with main substrate and two witness samples during deposition.

The base pressure prior to high temperature cleaning kept at 10⁻¹⁰ mbar region and prior to deposition was in the 10⁻⁸ mbar. The deposition was performed at 2×10⁻³ mbar of Kr for metal deposition and for nitride deposition (AlN or NbN) the total pressure was kept the same and the ratio of nitrogen to Kr was changed according to different deposition power used.

In total, there were deposited 16 samples of System 1 (Nb₃Sn) and 4 samples with Superconductor-Insulator-Superconductor (SIS) multilayer films. The deposition parameters for all samples are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2: List of samples and deposition parameters and layer structure

Date Sample ID	Substrate (witness)	Power supply	DC Bias (V)	Dep. temp (°C)	Time (min), Thickness (nm) Power (W) Current (A), Voltage (V)				
					Layer 1	Layer 2	Layer 3	Layer 4	Layer 5
19/04/18 A15-3	Cu	Pulse DC	0	380	Nb ₃ Sn 150', - 200 W 0.62 A, 322 V (350 kHz, 1.1 μs)				

06/07/18 A15-4	Cu	DC	0	550	Nb 240', - 400 W 0.85 A, 470 V	Nb ₃ Sn 120', - 200 0.41 A, 479 V			
18/07/18 A15-5	Sapphire	DC	0	550	Nb ₃ Sn 193', - 200 W 0.43 A, 470 V				
19/09/18 A15-6	Cu	DC	0	600	Nb ₃ Sn 187', - 200 W 0.39 A, 507 V				
21/09/18 A15-7	Cu	DC	0	450	Nb ₃ Sn 180, - 200 W 0.40 A, 502 V				
24/09/18 A15-8	Cu*	DC	0	28 Post annl. 600 °C delaminat ion	Nb ₃ Sn 120', - 200 W 0.41 A, 495 V				
26/09/18 A15-9	Cu* Heated to 600 °C → RT	DC	0	28 Post annl. 650 °C	Nb ₃ Sn 180', - 200 W 0.42 A, 472 V				
15/01/19 A15-11	Cu (Ta, Sapphire)	DC (AIN→ P DC)	0	650	Nb 240', - 400 W 1.09 A, 367 V	AIN 10', 25 nm 200 W 0.71 A, 280 V (350 kHz, 1.1 μs)	Nb ₃ Sn 30', 600 200 W 0.57,353		
17/01/19 A15-12	Cu (EP,LNL, L14) (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	650	Nb ₃ Sn 195' - 200 W 0.49 A, 404 V				
22/01/19 A15-13	Cu (EP, DL) (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	650	Nb ₃ Sn 195', - 200 W 0.50 A, 399 V				
24/01/19 A15-14	Cu (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	650	Nb 243', - 400 W 1.12 A, 358 V	Nb ₃ Sn 180', - 200 W 0.5 A, 402 V			
29/01/19 A15-15	Sapphire (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	650	Nb 238', - 400 W 1.14 A, 351 V	AIN 10', 25 nm 202 W 0.99 A, 280 V (350 kHz, 1.1 μs)	Nb ₃ Sn 40', 600 200 W 0.49, 404		

06/12/19 A15-16	Cu (SUBU, DL) (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	650	Nb ₃ Sn 180', - 200 W 0.50 A, 400 V				
11/02/19 A15-17	Cu (SUBU, DL), (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	650	Nb 240', - 400 W 1.17 A, 358 V	Nb ₃ Sn 180' - 200 W 0.50 A, 400 V			
14/02/19 A15-18	Cu (EP, LNL, L15) (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	600	Nb ₃ Sn 180', - 200 W 0.49 A, 411 V				
18/02/19 A15-19	Cu (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	650	Nb 208', - 400 W 1.17 A, 358 V	AlN 7', - 202 W 1.02 A, 196 V (350 kHz, 1.1 μs)	Nb ₃ Sn 5', - 200 W 0.53, 378	AlN 7', - 202 W 0.98 A, 203 V (350 kHz, 1.1 μs)	Nb ₃ Sn 5', - 200 W 0.54, 368
21/02/19 A15-20	Sapphire (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	650	Nb 247', - 400 W 1.11 A, 362 V	AlN 7', - 202 W 0.98 A, 204 V (350 kHz, 1.1 μs)	Nb ₃ Sn 5', - 200 W 0.54, 372	AlN 7', - 202 W 1.03 A, 195 V (350 kHz, 1.1 μs)	Nb ₃ Sn 5', - 200 W 0.56, 357
27/02/19 A15-21	Cu (Ta, Sapphire)	Pulsed DC	-80	300	Nb ₃ Sn 180', - 200 W 0.91 A, 220 V (350 kHz, 1.1 μs)				
06/03/19 A15-22	Cu (Ta, Sapphire)	Pulsed DC	-80	400	Nb ₃ Sn 191', - 200 W 0.80 A, 250 V (350 kHz, 1.1 μs)				
13/03/19 A15-23	Cu (Ta, Sapphire)	Pulsed DC	-80	400	NbN 191', - 400 W 1.25 A, 391 V (350 kHz, 1.1 μs)				

2.3. Nb₃SN DEPOSITION

Nb₃Sn films were deposited on copper substrate without any surface chemical polishing (EP or SUBU) preparation. The deposition was carried out at 650 °C (A15-6), 450 °C (A15-7) and at room temperature and post annealed at 650 °C (A15-9). The latter the substrate was heated to 650 °C for 20 hours and then cooled down to room temperature prior the deposition.

The results of DC magnetisation curve for normalized magnetic moment (M/M_i) as function of external field is shown in Fig. 4, as it can be seen that best performance in terms of superconducting properties is achieved by the film deposited at 650 °C (A15-9) where the film deviate slightly from the Meissner state even up to a field of 300 mT. The film deposited at room temperature and then post annealed (A15-6) has the worst performance since M/M_i drop sharply at very low field of about 10 mT. The film deposited at moderate temperature of 450 °C performs slightly better but its performance is much reduced. This is also evident in the critical temperature of sample A15-9 where the T_c is estimated to be 14.6 K in comparison to the sample A15-6 which depicted to have $T_c = 15.7$. In both cases the two samples are both below the ideal T_c reported for the Nb_3Sn which is 18 K.

Figure 4: (a) Normalized DC magnetization curves as a function of external applied field and (b) magnetization as a function of temperature for Nb_3Sn film deposited on copper for samples A15-6, A15-7 and A15-9.

The planar and X-section SEM together with the X-ray diffraction as shown in Fig. 5 depict that the film consists of small grain compact dense structure with reasonable sharp interface. The grain size calculated from the X-ray diffraction is in order of 8 to 10 nm which is almost twice the calculated coherent length of Nb_3Sn which is reported to be 4.2 nm. The lattice parameters has also been calculated to be 5.292 Å. The EDX analysis shown in Fig. 6 depicts the film composition is within the tolerance limit of superconducting phase of Nb_3Sn stoichiometry and impurity free within the detection limit. The reduction in T_c can be explained by the lack of long range order as well as small deviation from the stoichiometry.

Figure 5: Planar (a), X-section (b) SEM micrograph and (c) X-ray diffraction of sample A15-9.

element	atomic %
Cu L	0.06
N L	76.76
Sn L	23.18

Figure 6: Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis of Nb₃Sn sample A15-9 deposition at 650°C.

2.4. Nb₃Sn DEPOSITION IN BILAYER

The Nb/Nb₃Sn bilayer was deposited on copper in order to compare the performance of the thin film Nb₃Sn as a superconducting material suitable for SRF cavity fabrication. Samples A15-4, A15-14 and A15-17 was synthesised by depositing Nb₃Sn of top of 2.6 μm of Nb on as received (A15-4 and A15-14) and SUBU prepared (A15-17) copper substrate at 650 °C.

Figure 7 shows that the bilayer deposition resulted in two different distinct areas. The homogeneous area as demonstrated in Fig. 7 (a) and (b) the layer is grown in the intended structure. As it can be observed from the SEM cross section there is two distinct and well separated layer with sharp interface following contour of the layer roughness. The planar view also shows network of a well-defined large grains of Nb₃Sn densely packed at the surface. The scanning EDX line analysis presented in Fig. 8, depicts the purity of chemical state of the grown bilayer with some degree of mixed state at the interface which can be partly due to resolution of the analysis volume sampled by the analysing electron beam. One can also observe that the ratio of Nb counts level (Y axis in Fig. 8) drops by ~25% in the Nb₃Sn layer. Furthermore the level of other impurities such as oxygen and carbon is within the detection limit.

However as shown in Fig. 7 (c) and (d) the film has grown in a very complex structure. From both set of micrographs (cross section and plan view) one can clearly see the two layer of Nb and Nb₃Sn is completely intermixed and there is a substantial volume of copper substrate both in elemental and alloy form of copper-tin alloy is present throughout the depth of the layer and at the surface.

Figure 7: High resolution SEM micrograph of FIB X-section and planar view of sample A15-4 (a)-(b) pure Nb_3Sn area (c)-(d) segregated copper area.

Figure 8: EDX line scan of homogenous area of sample 15-4.

Figures 9 and 10 illustrate the elemental mapping determined by EDX analysis of the surface and the x-section of the area presented in Fig. 7 (c) and (d), respectively. The surface is a mix of copper-tin alloy, Nb₃Sn and copper. A similar mix is also evident starting from the copper interface and extended all the way through up to the surface.

Figure 9: EDX elemental mapping of the area of the surface presented in Fig. 7(c). (a) carbon, (b) oxygen, (c) aluminium, (d) copper, (e) tin and (f) niobium.

Figure 10: EDX elemental mapping of the area of the surface presented in figure 7c. (a) oxygen, (b) copper, (c) aluminium, (d) silicon, (e) niobium and (f) tin.

Figure 11(a) displays the normalized magnetic moment of the film as function of applied external magnetic field. A drop in M/M_i ratio from 1 represents the onset of flux penetration and deviation from the Meissner state of superconducting film. In contrast with Nb_3Sn deposited as a single layer but in exactly the same condition, the onset of the drop in magnetisation starts at a much lower field of 50 mT. The critical temperature of the Nb_3Sn layer is found to be at 17.8 K as shown is in Fig. 11(b) which is much closer to the reported value of 18 K however the drop is not gradual which is can be due to presence mixed phases or area of Sn deficient or some other type of defects such as impurities as discussed above or complex dislocation or simple defects such as vacancies and interstitials. The critical temperature of the Nb layer is found to be at 8.9 K which is 0.3 K lower than the usual thin film Nb but the drop is sharp.

Figure 11: a) Normalized dc magnetization curves as a function of external applied field and b) magnetization as a function of temperature for Nb_3Sn/Nb bilayer film deposited on copper for samples A15-4.

Figure 12 represents the grazing incident X-ray Diffraction (GIXRD) of the sample A15-4. The diffracted peaks match well with variety Nb_3Sn stored data. The analysis shows a grain size of 120 Å and a lattice parameters of 5.29 Å.

Figure 12: Grazing incident X ray diffraction (GIXRD) of the sample A15-4 (Nb_3Sn/Nb bilayer on copper).

2.5. SIS STRUCTURE OF $Nb_3Sn/AlN/Nb$ MULTILAYER ON COPPER

A series of double (A15-19 and A15-20) and single insulating (AlN) layer (A15-11 and A15-15) has been deposited on copper and sapphire and subsequently on their witness samples. As an example of the deposition structure two examples of single (AlN) layer as insulating layer in SIS structure deposited on the witness sample (Ta) will be presented. The sample were deposited on two separate run but under the same deposition condition with the main substrate being copper (A15-11) and sapphire (A15-15). The cross-section SEM with indicative layer thicknesses and the EXD chemical analysis of the x-section is shown in Figs. 13 and 14 for samples of A15-15 and A15-11, respectively.

Figure 15 display the normalised DC magnetic moment of $Nb_3Sn/AlN/Nb$ SIS multilayer film deposited on copper for samples A15-11, the deviation from the Meissner state starts at an applied external field of 80 mT which resembles to those of Nb single layer deposited on copper rather than Nb_3Sn observed above which the film stayed in Meissner state up to field of 300 mT. The full cycle hysteresis loop shows a smooth curve over the full range of applied field which means that the film has stable flux pinning.

Figure 13: Sample A15-15, (a) High resolution SEM of ion milled X-section of SIS multilayer structure deposited on Ta. (b) EDX chemical mapping of the X-section.

Figure 14: Sample A15-11, (a) High resolution SEM of ion milled X-section of SIS multilayer structure deposited on Ta. (b) EDX chemical mapping of the X-section.

Figure 15: (a) Normalized dc magnetization curves as a function of external applied field at 4.2 K and (b) full cycle hysteresis curve at 4.2 K magnetization as a function of temperature for $Nb_3Sn/AlN/Nb$ SIS multilayer film deposited on copper for samples A15-11.

3. System 2 – Niobium Nitride (NbN) at University of Siegen

3.1 DEPOSITION FACILITY

As part of initial studies into NbN thin film deposition, five films were deposited onto copper and silicon substrates with DC magnetron sputtering at different N₂ % for morphological, topographical and superconducting characterisation. The results of these samples were presented at the 8th Thin Films Workshop in Legnaro (Italy).

Based on the analysis of the superconducting properties of these initial NbN samples at IEE, a second set of samples was completed with a more focused N₂ % during deposition, focused around 25% N₂. Five new samples were deposited with the following parameters:

- Deposition temperature: 650 °C;
- Nitrogen percentage (based on flow control): 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 %;
- Deposition pressure (total): 1.5×10^{-2} hPa;
- Film thickness: 0.8 ± 0.2 μm.

These films were deposited with the express intention of determining whether initial delamination of NbN films was due to film thickness induced stresses. This has proven to be true and the new films with lower thicknesses have shown no signs of delamination. The new set of films are currently at IEE for superconducting characterisation.

In order to gain a broader understanding of the effects of the deposition parameters on the resultant NbN thin films, a large parametrical investigation has been undertaken. A series of NbN thin films have been deposited onto Copper and Silicon substrates as part of a screening study to determine the optimum deposition parameters for NbN thin films on copper for SRF applications. The NbN samples were synthesised in a randomized order developed through the use of a design of experiments function in OriginPro data analysis software. The function also completely randomised the deposition process. The randomisation of runs aims to confound any effects which would be present if the films were deposited in a linear fashion. Table 3 shows the parameter field of this study. Overall, a total of 36 samples were produced.

Table 3. Parameter window of the randomised screening study for the deposition of NbN thin films on Si and Cu.

Parameter boundary	Substrate Temperature, T_S [°C]	Pressure p [mPa]	Substrate Bias, U_B [V]	N ₂ content, c_N [%]	Process Gas	Cathode Power, P [W]
high (+)	600	1600	-80	30	Ar	500
low (-)	200	800	0	10	Kr	300

In the following paragraphs, for a convenient sample declaration, the parameter set is given as plusses “+” and minuses “-” in brackets for the respective high and low parameter boundary. The order of the parameters is the same as in Table 3. For example, sample 14 has a parameter set of (- - + + + +), meaning $T_S = 200$ °C, $p = 800$ mPa, $U_B = -80$ V, $c_N = 30$ %, Ar, and $P = 500$ W.

Prior to the deposition of the NbN films, the copper substrates were prepared in the following manner:

- Mechanically polished to a roughness of $S_q = 35$ nm \pm 18 nm;
- Ultra sonic degrease in acetone – 15 mins;
- Ultra sonic degrease in ethanol – 15 mins;
- Chemical etch in HNO₃:H₂O (distilled) in a 3:2 ratio – 30 seconds;
- Rinsed with distilled water;
- Blow dry with N₂.

Following the blow dry with N₂, the samples are placed directly into the deposition chamber.

In order to ensure comparability of samples, the following procedure has been followed for all samples prior to the deposition of the NbN film:

- Deposition chamber (with the substrate loaded) baked out at 650 °C for 6 hours;
- Deposition chamber pumped down (with heating off) to a base pressure 5×10^{-7} hPa;
- Sputter clean of target cathode;
- Sputter cleaning (etching) of substrates.

Once these steps have been completed, the deposition of the NbN film is completed according to the pre-determined list of experimental parameters. The films are all within a film thickness band of 1.2 μ m \pm 0.2 μ m.

Once the deposition run is completed, the deposition chamber is allowed to cool down and the samples are removed and placed in a sample holder. Immediately following removal from the deposition chamber, the samples are loaded in an SEM machine for characterisation by SEM and EDX. This allows direct comparability of oxygen content, as the films have all seen the same amount of time exposed to atmosphere (as short as possible) prior to analysis with EDX.

Following investigation of the samples in the SEM, the samples are taken to the confocal microscope for large scale surface roughness characterisation. Samples will also be subjected to Rutherford Backscattering (RBS) measurements for a more quantitative determination of the nitrogen content. Some samples will be sent to STFC for forwarding to a previously used laboratory and some samples will be sent to Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH for characterisation. The tests in Jülich require further deposition of the NbN films onto Carbon substrates.

An interesting development which has been found is the possible deposition of an interlayer of Nb between the copper substrate and the NbN film during the sputter cleaning phase prior to deposition. This was observed during a failure of one coating process and will require further

investigation. It is possible that all of the NbN films have been deposited with a Nb interlayer of roughly 80 nm thickness. This interlayer is evident in some of the SEM images.

3.2 THIN FILM ANALYSIS (TASK 15.3)

Directly after the coating all samples have been investigated by SEM and EDX. Figure 16 shows a selection of cross-sectional and plain-view micrographs of NbN thin films on Si and Cu, respectively. From this analysis, a couple of important information can be extracted. The substitution of Ar with Kr as working gas does not change the growth modes significantly within this parameter window. The same holds true for the lower and upper boundary of the N_2 content. Due to parameter interdependency, no significant tendencies for the substrate temperature T_S are found, owing the statistical analysis of upcoming characterisations. For a dense film a high T_S is preferred, but not mandatory provided that a substrate bias and high cathode power is applied. This becomes obvious in Sample 14 (- - + + +), which is shown in Fig. 16 (e). Here a dense and compact grown film can be seen with no individual columns. The process pressure p has high impact on the growth mechanism. Fig. 16 (g) to (j) show the samples 35 (+ - - + +) and 36 (+ + - - +), respectively. A high p (sample 36) tend to grow a very porous and highly columnar film structure. These columns grow from substrate to the surface forming individual grains, which are barely interconnected. Whereas, sample 35 deposited at low pressure shows very dense and adherent columns. However, this effect can be suppressed by applying a substrate bias U_B . Sample 8 (+ + + + +) and 32 (+ - + + - +) reveal this effect in the respective Fig. 16 (a) to (d). Both cross-sections show a very dense and compact grown film regardless of p . Finally, a high cathode power P in nearly all cases is needed for a dense film. An applied U_B can compensate a lack of P , provided that there is a high enough mean-free-path (p is low), see sample 20 (- - + + - -) in Fig. 16 (k) and (l).

Additionally to the above findings one effect becomes prominent in many NbN samples deposited on Cu: the high tendency of patterning of the coatings due to the different crystallographic orientation of the polycrystalline Cu substrate (surface decoration). Figure 17 shows the low-resolution plain view micrographs of two different NbN films on Cu.

Together with the SEM investigations above, all samples have been analysed by means of EDX. The measurement was performed in both, cross-sectional on Si and plain-view on Cu. Figure 18 shows two spectra of representative samples. The analysis of sample 14 in Fig. 18 (a) shows no signs of contamination, especially no Oxygen. Sample 36 in Fig. 18 (b) shows a slight Oxygen contribution. The source of oxygen may be derived from oxidation of the Nb-rich film, given that the Oxygen peak is present in the low- N_2 (10% flow-rate) samples only. A stoichiometric investigation of the Nb_xN_y films by means of e.g. RBS is in progress to shed some light on this matter.

Figure 16: SEM micrographs of NbN thin films on silicon (cross-section) and copper (plain-view).

Figure 17: SEM plain-view micrographs of NbN on Cu.

Figure 18: EDX spectra of NbN films on Cu in plain-view with (a) 30% and (b) 10% N₂ flow rate during the synthesis.

4. Superconductivity evaluation at IEE

Flat samples with a superconducting layer deposited on different substrates were received from the partners. The University of Siegen (Siegen Uni) provided samples with NbN superconducting layer deposited on Cu substrates at different partial pressure of Nitrogen in the deposition atmosphere. STFC provided samples with Nb₃Sn layer deposited on Cu, Sapphire and Ta substrates, either with no buffer layer, with Nb buffer layer and with Nb/AlN buffer/insulation layer.

In the first step the samples were characterised by measuring virgin DC magnetization curves on small measurement samples of approximately 2 mm × 2 mm. In the case of the NbN samples from Siegen Uni the measurement samples were cut at IEE with the help of a laboratory cut-off machine (saw) using a SiC cut-off disc. Measurements samples of the Nb₃Sn layers on Cu substrates were prepared (cut) at STFC. Samples of the layers on the

Figure 19: The Quantum Design PPMS system at IEE.

other two substrates were prepared at IEE, the Sapphire substrate samples by cleaving and the Ta samples by cutting with scissors as the Ta substrates were relatively thin and it was very complicated to fix them on a supporting plate for cutting. Several of the Ta substrate samples were unfortunately damaged (the samples are no longer flat, the edges are bent) in the preparation procedure.

In the magnetization measurements, the component of the magnetic moment (m) of the sample parallel to the external applied magnetic field B was measured, using Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM) option of the commercial PPMS system from Quantum Design Inc., shown in Fig. 19. The magnetic moment m was measured in dependence on monotonically increasing (or decreasing) applied field B , recording the so-called magnetization curves $m(B)$. The magnetization curves were measured on samples cooled down below T_c in zero applied magnetic field (zero-field-cooled conditions, ZFC). The external magnetic field was applied perpendicular to the flat face of the samples. The main characteristic determined from the magnetization curves is the so-called first flux entry field B_{en} . It is the applied field at which the magnetic flux starts entering the sample's volume. It was detected as the field at which the virgin magnetization curve starts to deviate from the linear dependence that the virgin curve follows in the initial part starting from the zero applied field, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 20. The field B_{en} was determined employing 2% relative difference criterion, i.e. as the applied field at which the relative difference between the virgin magnetization

curve and the initial linear trend reaches 2%. B_{en} is proportional to the first (lower) critical field B_{c1} through a geometrical constant that depends on the dimensions of the sample.

Figure 20: Illustration of determination of the characteristic field B_{en} from the virgin magnetization curves.

Comparison in the Fig. 21 shows that the B_{en} for all NbN samples are considerably below the range of B_{en} values determined for the series of Nb samples studied in the year 1. The Nb₃Sn samples show a wide spread of B_{en} values, the highest B_{en} 's are comparable with the highest ones of the Nb samples while the lowest B_{en} 's are well below the range of Nb samples.

Figure 21: The first flux entry field B_{en} , determined applying the 2% relative difference criterion, at 4.22 K. All the samples on Cu substrates tested so far (Nb, NbN and Nb₃Sn materials) are compared.

Very interestingly, the highest (samples 22/01/19, 06/02/19) as well as the lowest (samples 14/02/19, 17/01/19) values were determined for the same layer sequence – the Nb₃Sn layer deposited directly on the Cu substrate. In case of the highest B_{en} values the substrate was prepared (either by EP or SUBU cleaning procedure) directly at STFC shortly before the deposition. In case of the lowest B_{en} values the substrates were prepared/cleaned originally at the INFN Legnaro lab (LNL) and were delivered to STFC longer time before the actual Nb₃Sn deposition. Probably the surface quality of the substrates may have degraded during the storage time. Comparison of the Nb₃Sn samples at different substrates in the Fig. 22 shows that the B_{en} results for the Sapphire substrate samples are either comparable or prevailing slightly lower than for the corresponding Cu substrate sample. The only exception are the samples 14/02/19, 17/01/19 discussed above where the B_{en} of the Sapphire substrate sample is considerably higher than of the Cu substrate sample. Figure 21 also shows that all the other layer configurations containing the Nb buffer and/or AlN insulation layers, or the double layer configuration, yield for the moment smaller B_{en} than the Nb₃Sn layer deposited directly on the Cu substrate.

Figure 22: The first flux entry field B_{en} determined applying the 2% relative difference criterion, at 4.22 K. Comparison of all Nb_3Sn samples deposited on different substrates (Cu, Sapphire, Ta). D – indicates the damaged samples on Ta substrate.

5. Discussion

5.1. SYSTEM 1 (Nb_3Sn)

Based on the results presented above in Fig. 4, the best superconducting properties among the deposited and tested Nb_3Sn samples were demonstrated on the samples deposited on Cu at high temperature (around 550-650 °C). On the other hand, the samples deposited at room temperature show no superconducting properties. However, the latter showed the some superconductivity after being post annealed at 600 °C. In general, Nb_3Sn look a good material for a single layer coating and should be further explored at RF conditions.

Depositing bilayer film (first Nb film followed by Nb_3Sn film) aimed to synthesise the system which is similar to bulk Nb cavity with a Nb_3Sn layer produced by Sn diffusion process. The magnetisation can be explained by superposition of Nb and Nb_3Sn film signals. Although the DC magnetometry provides valuable information for the superconducting properties of materials, it is not suitable for

complex systems like Nb/Nb₃Sn or SIS and should be studied with a different technique such as magnetic field penetration, choke cavity, QPR (all planned for Year 3) and, finally, in a real cavity.

It should be noted that the EDX and SEM results have shown (see Figs. 8-11) that there are some areas that have grown in a non-homogeneous structure. This was caused by diffusion of Cu from a substrate into a bilayer. Such defects can be detrimental in the performance and the RF cavity operating in the RF field. This problem should be addressed further in future.

5.2. SIS SYSTEM (Nb₃Sn/AlN/Nb)

Four SIS systems were deposited and characterised. The thickness of the insulation layer was varied between 10 and 30 nm and the thickness of screening Nb₃Sn film was varied between 50 and 600 nm. The DC magnetisation results shown in Fig. 15 are dominated by Nb (as a volume ratio of Nb to Nb₃Sn is 3:1). As it was mentioned above, the DC magnetometry is not directly explanatory for complex systems, it is therefore not sensitive to the defects shown in Fig. 14.

Since in both bilayer and SIS the defects persist to exist the screening film should be selected from a material meeting the following criteria:

- It should be thermally stable (for example: Nb₃Sn is unstable because it becomes deficient Sn at high temperature);
- Since insulating layer (AlN) contains nitrogen it is reasonable to choose from the nitrides materials such as NbN and NbTiN.

5.3. SYSTEM 2 (NbN)

The first flux entry fields B_{en} of the first two batches of NbN on Cu samples shown above in Fig. 19 are all below the other samples of Nb and Nb₃Sn. However, there is a trend in lower N₂ flow leading to a higher B_{en} . The newly prepared samples shown in Table 3 in the parameter study are now optimised with respect to N content. Furthermore, the in-depth film structure study by SEM (see Fig. 16) revealed a strong parameter interdependency of cathode power, substrate bias, substrate temperature, and process pressure as described in section 3.2. The main issue of ceramic thin films (NbN) on metals (Cu) is the lower adatom diffusivity and higher ratio of substrate surface energy to film surface energy compared to metal films on metal substrates (Nb or Nb₃Sn on Cu). This leads to the above shown highly columnar growth mode with a strong tendency to conical columns. The latter causes many lattice defects and possibly micrometre sized pores (finite-size effect and shadowing). This, in turn, leads to high scattering of electrons and many pinning centres for magnetic field lines. With the extensive parameter study above it is now possible to produce enhanced NbN films with respect to the film structure. At the time of writing of this report, the latest samples are on the way from Siegen to IEE to be measured. Concluding, the NbN thin films need more optimisation and this comprehensive study is the perfect framework to assess their applicability in future accelerators.

6. Future plans / Conclusion / relation to other ARIES work

- Nb₃Sn can be successfully deposited from an alloy target and demonstrate good SC properties when it is deposited at high temperature (around 550-650 °C).
- Complex defects can be formed in when Nb₃Sn is deposited in a multilayer structure.
- NbN can be produced from an Nb metal target by reactive sputtering in N₂ rich atmosphere. The optimisation of the film's structure is possible at well selected parameter settings. If NbN can compete with Nb or Nb₃Sn in terms of SC properties, it will be shown in upcoming studies.
- For SIS structures, the screening layer materials should be one containing nitrogen such as NbN and NbTiN, especially when the insulation layer is AlN.
- DC magnetometry is an insufficient technique for multilayer characterisation of superconducting properties. The WP15 team should focus on development of:
 - 3rd harmonics at CEA (operational) and IEE (presently under commissioning),
 - magnetic field penetration at STFC (presently under commissioning) and
 - RF measurements at CERN (operational), HZB (operational) and STFC (presently under commissioning).

7. References

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8. Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AFM	Atomic Force Microscope
CEA	The French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission (Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique)
CERN	European Council for Nuclear Research
EDS	Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometry
EP	Electropolishing
HZB	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
IEE	Institute of Electrical Engineering, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava
INFN	Italian Institute of Nuclear Physics - Legnaro National Laboratories
IPA	Isopropanol alcohol
OFHC	Oxygen-Free High thermal Conductivity copper
OFE	Oxygen Free Electronic copper
PPMS	Physical Property Measurement System
QPR	Quadrupole Resonator
QWR	Quarter Wave Resonator
RF	Radio Frequency
RTU	Riga Technical University
SC	Superconductivity
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
SRF cavity	Superconducting Radio Frequency cavity

STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council - Daresbury Laboratory
SUBU	Chemical Polishing of Cu with a solution of Sulphamic Acid and Buthanol
XRD	X-Ray Diffraction